

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

The Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox is a method collection to support interdisciplinary teamwork. These methods are organized by four key aspects of interdisciplinarity:

- they structure the **#onboarding** time,
- favor establishing **#common ground**,
- enable **#cooperation**,
- and help deal with **#differences**.

#onboarding

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Team Profile Matrix

Mapping profiles of each team members on a twodimensional matrix. Goal: Mapping the diversity of team profiles and introducing individual profiles. When: Onboarding, at first encounter of a team or new project

Preparation

- 1 provide whiteboard or flipchart
- 2 based on participant information and later intended project work, identify two relevant binary parameters of distinction (e.g. prev. experience “Academia/Industry” vs project role: “Designer/Developer”)

Instructions

- 1 facilitator draws a 2-parameter orthogonal matrix on whiteboard
- 2 ask each participant to introduce themselves and
- 3 position themselves on the matrix.

#onboarding

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Team Manifesto

Teams jointly complete a „Team Manifesto“, discussing on their purpose, goals and responsibilities. They agree on procedures for information sharing, decision making, problem solving and relationship building. Goal: shorten the time teams spend forming and storming by clarifying purpose and process. When: To be completed by the whole team initial to the collaboration. It can be preceded by the Team Story method, to start with a common vision of the process.

Preparation

- 1 print one template per team

Instructions

- 1 provide enough time for teams to discuss and jointly complete
- 2 all members sign the vision statement
- 3 define a later date for a review of the charter, as a living document.

#commonground

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Team Story

This method allows different team members to retrospectively look at their joint process. Goal: build a joint narrative of team process. When: in retrospect at the end of group process.

Preparation

- 1 Provide wide format, wall-scale paper and markers

Instructions

- 1 In group: draw a simple timeline, indicating the start and end dates
- 2 In group: further structure the timeline, e.g. into project parts, organizational levels, or process phases.
- 3 individually identify key events (even those that hindered the process)
- 4 based on the individual elements, the group jointly creates a storywall picture of their process, representing their group's collective understanding.
- 5 (optional) add the main lessons learned.

#commonground

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Reflecting Team

A method allowing for having and witnessing open conversations

Goal: critical reflections in teams. When: During ongoing team projects, or in situations of conflict. Also in retrospect, at the end of a project.

Preparation

- 1 Organise an undisturbed space
- 2 Explain procedure, obtain consent from all involved

Instructions

- 1 Group splits into 2 sections, according to disciplines
- 2 The reflecting team (section 1) sits in a circle. The others (section 2) turn their back to the circle, so that they can listen, but not interfere.
- 3 Section 1 share their thoughts about the group process.
- 4 Section 2 process their thoughts about section 1's reflections.
- 5 Both sections come together to debrief.

#cooperation

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Playful Fiction

This method uses roleplay and improvisation techniques to (re-)enact relevant team situations.

Goal: to stimulate conversations among different perspectives. When: During ongoing team projects, used to explore a personal dilemma, replay a live experience, or prepare for an upcoming conversation.

Preparation

- 1 Prepare a scenario and situation to be explored (replay or preparation)
- 2 Define two to several roles for acting out this situation.

Instructions

- 1 Ask participants to take a role. Give them 5-10min to prepare it.
- 2 Give people a name tag. Ask them to sit or stand. Use props, lighting etc
- 3 start acting in first person.
- 4 Stop when something significant has happened. Reflect in the group.
- 5 When a suggestion comes up, ask the person to play out the suggestion.

#cooperation

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Novella Play

This method stimulates conversation among different perspectives and is played out as a roleplay in written form, possibly online.

It allows exploring a constellation of different stakeholders. When: at the beginning, or during an ongoing collaboration.

Preparation

- 1 Prepare a scenario and situation to be explored.
- 2 Create a people card for each stakeholder, with attributes and intentions.

Instructions

- 1 Each player receives a people card and prepares to play their character.
- 2 Write a prose description of how your character enters the scenario.
- 3 Then pass the turn to the next person who will continue writing the story from their own character's perspective. Describe impressions and thoughts. What do they notice? How do they interpret what is said?
- 4 Reflect on the dialogue in the group, when completed.

#differences

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Nomadic Concepts

Discuss definitions of significant terms and concepts. A heuristic tool for exchanging understandings of concepts across disciplinary, professional and cultural boundaries.

Goal: Getting a broader conceptual apparatus for problem framing and knowledge production. When: before or at an early stage of a collaboration.

Preparation

- 1 identify concepts relevant to the participants, broad enough to be of importance to all disciplines represented. e.g. „digital“, „virtual“, „data“, „idea“, „prototype“, „creative“.
- 2 select and print core texts on respective concepts

Instructions

- 1 In groups of 2-3, articulate your respective definition of the concept, discuss differences and reflect on its use in various communities.
- 2 read a short provided text, defining or referring to the concept. Discuss again. Pay attention to new insights.

#differences

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Opposites

Participants articulate opposites of given terms. A playful approach for exploring concepts across disciplines.

Goal: Insights into how widely concepts can be understood within and across disciplines.
When: early stage of collaboration, ideally in a class or in a group of several project teams.

Preparation

- 1 identify 6 relevant adjectives, that may have ambivalent meaning (e.g. user-centered, virtual, interactive, immersive).
- 2 print copies of the adjectives on small strips of paper. Colour-code the papers for respective disciplines (e.g. green for developers).

Instructions

- 1 facilitator hands out 6 different paper strips per participant
- 2 articulate the opposite of the adjective, write it on the back of the strip. time pressure, 20 secs per adjective.
- 3 all: cluster responses, grouped by adjective and colour/discipline
- 4 all: review the clustered responses, discuss surprising findings.

#differences

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Project Builder

A hands-on approach, using bricks to represent the same project work from different angles, and reflect on possibly different understandings of the common endeavour.

Goal: Insights on different disciplinary perspectives on a current project. When: Intermediate stage within a project collaboration, during an ongoing project.

Preparation

- 1 Provide a box of assorted building bricks

Instructions

- 1 team members split up, and spatially separate
- 2 individually build your current project out of bricks
- 3 after 20 minutes, the teams rejoin and mutually present their constructions. They are encouraged to discuss different perspectives and framings of the same project, seen from different angles.

#differences

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Dialogue Approach

The approach consists of a set of questions and statements used to evoke dialogue in a workshop format.

Goal: Participants become aware of their own disciplinary thought style and the disciplinary thought style of their collaborators / about different assumptions and positions. When: before / or at an early stage of a collaboration.

Preparation

- 1 prepare relevant, open ended questions
- 2 print each question on one sheet, as
handout

Instructions

- 1 in disciplinary mixed groups of 2-5, discuss
your question.
- 2 present your discussion to the plenum,
rephrase other positions.

#commonground

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Team Persona

The team describes itself comparatively as a person, a car or a vacation destination. Metaphorically, they express their ideas and values for working together.

Goal: Makes the implicit assumptions about the team and collaboration clear. When: Good at the start of a collaboration to clarify expectations. Also suitable as a preparation for the „Team Manifesto“ method.

Preparation

- 1 choose terms
- 2 prepare workshop materials

Instructions

Facilitator guides discussion and makes notes on flipchart

- 1 if your team was a person, who would it be? (age, name, profession, etc.)
- 2 if your team were a shopping store, what kind of store?
- 3 discuss, if your team were a car, what kind of car?

#cooperation

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Three in One

This method is used to examine a dilemma or negotiation from different viewpoints and walk in someone else's shoes.

Goal: allows participants to inhabit different viewpoints within a negotiation and contextualize one's viewpoint within a team. When: It is best used when decisions are made, and the team needs to agree on solutions.

Preparation

- 1 participants form groups of two: a case giver and a sparring partner (who is not involved in the situation to be explored)
- 2 Two chairs are needed per group and enough space to rearrange and walk around the chairs

Instructions

- 1 Think of a situation where you and other collaborators have differing viewpoints.
- 2 Get a partner and face each other, sitting on two chairs. Describe your point of view to your partner: how you see it, what you aim for, how you feel about it. Your partner listens neutrally.
- 3 After five minutes, switch chairs. Now you (the same person as before) speak but try to represent the viewpoint of the other party, as if it was your own.
- 4 After five minutes, you both stand up and face the two chairs. Have a conversation as two neutral observers: what have we heard from both parties? How are they interacting with each other? What advice would we give them?

#onboarding

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Team Painting

Participants are asked to paint an aquarelle based on a piece of music or a video. They are then clustered into teams, based on the diversity of their paintings.

An intuitive method for forming teams based on associative criteria. When: Before a collaboration, at a team composition stage.

Preparation

- 1 Select media, e.g. audio-file or youtube-movie
- 2 Prepare drawing materials

Instructions

- 1 Play media to group.
- 2 Participants are asked to remain silent and individually paint their impressions, with identical instructions (e.g. with a brush and 3 primary colours).
- 3 The moderator clusters the paintings so that each cluster is as heterogeneous as possible.

#commonground

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Positive Gossip

The participants express their appreciation of each other - behind their backs. A warm-up method to activate the resources of the team members, creating a positive basis for subsequent activities.

Goal: build mutual appreciation and trust among participants. When: best used at the beginning of a workshop or group process. If the participants do not yet know each other, the activity can be used hypothetically "I imagine that X has, is, can..."

Preparation

- 1 Provide chairs in groups of three.
- 2 two people sit behind the back of the third one, who faces away from the others.

Instructions

- 1 The first two people start saying positive things about the third person, based on their skills, recent contributions, or on their attitudes and values.
- 2 After two minutes, the participants turn their chairs and take turns.
- 3 When all three had their turn, sit together in a round and reflect on what you heard about yourself.

#commonground

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Anyone who...

This activity helps participants introduce themselves and creates a safe space by identifying common properties or experiences between them.

Goal: establish common ground and trust among participants. When: at the beginning of a workshop or team process, when participants do not know each other yet.

Preparation

- 1 Provide chairs, number of participants minus one.
- 2 Have team members sit on chairs in a circle, with one person standing in the center.

Instructions

- 1 The standing person describes a property or experience.
- 2 Anyone who also shares that fact (including themselves) must stand up and find a new seat.
- 3 the new person then starts over...

#commonground

Interdisciplinary Team Toolbox

Story of Self Us Now

This method builds a shared understanding and mission for a team, community or cohort.

Goal: Identifying parallels between individual backgrounds, motivations, and goals to create urgency and encourage collective action. When: Best suited at the start of a collaboration.

Preparation

- 1 Provide paper and pencils for each person.
- 2 Prepare good guiding questions for each step of the activity.

Instructions

- 1 Participants individually draw up their «Story of Self», answering questions like: what inspires you? what are your strengths? what do you bring to the team?
- 2 The team joins together, and each participant shares their story to the others.
- 3 The team reflects on the overlap in the stories and identifies common ground between team members. Then, they collaboratively create a «Story of Us». How do we define the «Us» of the team? What useful metaphor or image supports this story?
- 4 Next, they describe the current challenge: this is the «Story of Now» – why is it important for us to work on X? What are our hopes for achieving this? Why is «Now» the pivotal moment to act? How do we know we've achieved success?